

The NFDIxCS Artifact Evaluation Platform

Track: RDM Infrastructures

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Abstract

To achieve good and FAIR research data or software (artifacts), these artifacts should exhibit certain levels of quality [1]. Therefore, artifact evaluation tracks have been established in conferences as a means for quality assurance. In these tracks, researchers (authors) submit their artifacts, which are reviewed by other researchers (reviewers). With successful reviews, authors earn badges, which express met quality criteria. To support artifact evaluation tracks, the NFDIxCS consortium provides a self-hosted instance of HotCRP [2] as the NFDIxCS Artifact Evaluation Platform (AEP).¹ All components and extensions of the AEP are open source.

HotCRP is a web-based platform for managing conference review processes [2]. In the context of the AEP, we apply it for artifact evaluations to provide an infrastructure for these processes [3]. Concretely, the chairs of an artifact evaluation track can setup and configure a dedicated page for their track. In addition, they can customize forms for submitting artifacts and reviews to match a conference's needs and criteria. This enables chairs, for example, to include the selection of badges in both forms. As a consequence, authors can select the badges for which they apply, and reviewers can select the badges with which the authors should be awarded. Usually, the artifacts themselves are uploaded on a different platform, intended for, for instance, long term archival, and authors only put a link to the artifact in the AEP.

After all artifacts have been submitted, reviewers can bid for the artifacts that they want to review. Based on the bids, the chairs can assign the actual reviewers to artifacts so that they can start reviewing. During the review, reviewers can download the artifacts via the links from the submission forms. Furthermore, authors and reviewers can exchange pseudonymized comments to clarify issues or questions. Authors are also usually allowed to update their artifacts if necessary (e.g., to fix a bug). Reviewers complete their review by filling out the review form. The AEP supports both single and double blind reviews. Based on the reviews, the chairs can decide on the awarded badges and can notify the authors.

¹<https://ae.nfdixcs.org>

With the AEP, we have already hosted the artifact evaluation tracks of the International Conference on Software Architecture 2024 and 2025. Currently, we are conducting a survey within the latest supported track to gather feedback and aspects to improve. Additionally, we explore Cloud Development Environments for reviewing artifacts in a cloud-based environment to ease the review process. Moreover, we also work on improving the technical setup of the AEP to enable other institutions to host their own instance of the AEP. Lastly, we are integrating the Research Data Management Container from NFDIxCS [4] into artifact evaluations to facilitate reviews for such containers.

Resources

- Artifact Evaluation in the Context of NFDIxCS. <https://nfdixcs.org/meldung/artifact-evaluation-in-the-context-of-nfdixcs>. "A blog post about how NFDIxCS supported the artifact evaluation track of the International Conference on Software Architecture 2024."
- HotCRP Extended by NFDIxCS. <https://gitlab.kit.edu/kitel/sdq/research-projects/nfdixcs/hotcrp>. "GitLab repository with an independent fork of HotCRP with extensions provided by NFDIxCS. It is the main component of the AEP"
- HotCRP Extended by NFDIxCS. <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/swh:1:dir:c203a1deb4cad88651dcaadb569ebcac7774ac64;origin=https://gitlab.kit.edu/kitel/sdq/research-projects/nfdixcs/hotcrp.git;visit=swh:1:snp:b8fd8f690451ff367e55aea95cbe98952979ca93;anchor=swh:1:rev:43f0009c33f69c174a9d5d0190592d072f3b3cea>. "Current version 3.0.0-nfdixcs.3 of the independent fork of HotCRP, archived in the Software Heritage Archive."
- NFDIxCS Artifact Evaluation Platform Docker. <https://gitlab.kit.edu/kitel/sdq/research-projects/nfdixcs/ae-platform-docker>. "GitLab repository with a Docker compose setup to run the AEP"
- NFDIxCS Artifact Evaluation Platform Docker. <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/swh:1:dir:ac9b4a8e82701d1767973ffa8a9aa0c03f2b76b4;origin=https://gitlab.kit.edu/kitel/sdq/research-projects/nfdixcs/ae-platform-docker.git;visit=swh:1:snp:e4e106c1334e89a29cc8e2c23943e7becf334c1e;anchor=swh:1:rev:8a6c2b8a51d48571ba7626dd6c76e54e4cc3c2f5>. "Current version 0.3.0 of the NFDIxCS Artifact Evaluation Platform Docker repository, archived in the Software Heritage Archive."
- NFDIxCS Artifact Evaluation Platform Frontpage. <https://gitlab.kit.edu/kitel/sdq/research-projects/nfdixcs/ae-platform-front>. "GitLab repository with the landing page of the AEP"
- NFDIxCS Artifact Evaluation Platform Frontpage. <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/swh:1:dir:805c7990d9aabb1cc14770245b19a8e4932033bd;origin=https://gitlab.kit.edu/kitel/sdq/research-projects/nfdixcs/ae-platform-front.git;visit=swh:1:snp:230e8621b0f6b44a1cc111e27367cab3b31;anchor=swh:1:rev:a583b3835e5d6d9710983f4625fe7d1f229520c1>. "Current version 0.1.2 of the NFDIxCS Artifact Evaluation Platform Frontpage repository, archived in the Software Heritage Archive."
- HotCRP Conference Review Software. <https://github.com/kohler/hotcrp>. "The official GitHub repository of HotCRP, a web-based conference review management platform."

- HotCRP Conference Review Software. <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/swh:1:dir:bc45bc55262073b7e8c33eee9b85a51bfbc332fb;origin=https://github.com/kohler/hotcrp;visit=swh:1:snp:1d6d2571fbb31bde93761ff856580122cfcaeaanchor=swh:1:rev:b216ddc5e714e7a69ffed1916f939313666cc18>. "Current version 3.0.0 of HotCRP, on which the independent fork is based, archived in the Software Heritage Archive."

Author contributions

- Martin Armbruster: Conceptualization, Software, Writing – original draft
- Jan Bernoth: Conceptualization, Validation
- Michael Goedicke: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration
- Anne Koziolk: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Writing – review & editing

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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- [3] M. Armbruster, *Artifact evaluation in the context of nfdixcs*, Feb. 10, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://nfdixcs.org/meldung/artifact-evaluation-in-the-context-of-nfdixcs>.
- [4] J. Bernoth, S. I. Ayon, F. A. Laban, *et al.*, *Workflow for creating and sealing a research data management container (rdmc)*, Software Engineering 2025 – Companion Proceedings, 2025. DOI: [10.18420/se2025-ws-26](https://doi.org/10.18420/se2025-ws-26).